

JESUS AND NICODEMUS

An exegetical and theological reading of John 3:1–21

ABSTRACT

This paper offers a sustained exegetical and theological reading of John 3:1–21, centred on the nocturnal encounter between Jesus and Nicodemus. The study situates the dialogue within its immediate literary context (John 2:23–25), showing how Nicodemus stands at the threshold between sign-based, unstable belief and a deeper faith grounded in revelation. Particular attention is given to Jesus’s language of rebirth, exploring the polysemic force of ἀνωθεν as both “again” and “from above”, and to the parallelism between “seeing” and “entering” the Kingdom. The paper traces the movement from earthly metaphors to heavenly realities, culminating in the lifting up of the Son of man and the universal scope of divine love in John 3:16, 17. Finally, it reads the light/darkness motif as both narrative symbolism and existential summons. Nicodemus’s gradual disappearance from the dialogue is interpreted as deliberate, leaving the reader to complete the response that Nicodemus himself enacted—investigation, defence and finally open allegiance to Christ.

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JOHN 3

There was a man of the Pharisees named Nicodemus, a ruler of the Jews. (verse 1)

Jesus's visitor is introduced first by his gender, then his creed, then his name, then his station in life.

His station was in the highest court of the Jews—the Sanhedrin. This court was composed of seventy-one men drawn from the priesthood, the Sadducees, the scribes and the Pharisees (Acts 23:6). Here is *a* ruler of the Jews coming to consult *the* ruler of the Jews. The stage is set for a fascinating encounter.

John could have chosen not to give us Nicodemus's name. John does not tell us the names of a number of individuals who had significant encounters with Jesus. For example we do not know the name of the Samaritan lady at the well, or the name of the man born blind, or the important individual who pleaded that his servant might be healed. But we do know the name of this man, and he has a Greek name. What does his Greek name indicate? That he was born and brought up in the Jewish diaspora? Or even that he is the son of a proselyte? Furthermore, Nicodemus means “conqueror of the people”. His parents were certainly not unambitious. We can imagine them making sure that their son was sent to all the right schools, and their hopes for him regularly repeated to him. If the name is an indication of the driving ambitions of Nicodemus's parents, then Nicodemus has become a remarkably mellow and humble man.

Pharisees were scrupulous in their attendance upon the demands of the Mosaic Law and upon the demands of the Jewish traditions attached to it. It was the importance that the Pharisees attached to this punctilious observance of the Jewish traditions that immediately pitted them against Jesus. A Pharisee that has risen to the very top of the Jewish legal world would have a meticulous attitude to detail.

In the ensuing conversation, Jesus even refers to Nicodemus as “*the* teacher of Israel”. His name is sandwiched between his being a Pharisee and a ruler. This is quite some introduction for the man.

The mention of his gender as part of the brief introductory portrait seems at first to be unnecessary. However, the preceding verses state that when Jesus “was in

Jerusalem at the festival of the Passover, many people put their faith in his name when they saw the signs that he was performing. But Jesus would not entrust himself to them because he knew them all and because he did not need to have anyone bear witness about man, for he knew what was in man” (2:23–25).

The spectacular nature of Jesus’s miracles caused many to put faith in his name. John then tells us that Jesus would not entrust himself to these people. In other words, the trust was not mutual; Jesus knew that there was something insubstantial about the faith of these people, that it was temporarily based on the excitement of “the signs that he was performing”.

We may well have faith in Jesus, but does he have faith in us? “Can He count upon us ... for fidelity in times when much is needed?... He gives Himself to those who give themselves to Him...they who trust Him, not in one or two matters which they see He can manage, but absolutely in all things,—to these He will give Himself freely, sharing with them His work, His Spirit, His reward” (Dods).

Later, Jesus would say: “Unless you people see signs and wonders, you will never believe” (John 4:48). The final verse of chapter 2 states that Jesus “knew what was in man”. “He knew the fickleness and instability of the heart of man. He knew that a man can be swept away in a moment of emotion, and then back out when he discovers what [that] decision really means” (Barclay). So, will Jesus take the same attitude with Nicodemus as he took with the other excited people at the festival?

This one came to him in the night and said to him: “Rabbi, we know that you have come from God as a teacher, for no one can perform these signs that you perform unless God is with him.” (verse 2)

During the Passover Nicodemus wanted a private interview. There is no need to judge Nicodemus as having acted out of fear. Nicodemus himself stated the principle under which he, as a judge, lived his life: “Our Law does not judge a man unless it first hears from him and learns what he is doing, does it?” (John 7:51). Nicodemus wanted to hear from Jesus personally, before he made a decision, he wanted to meet the defendant for an interview free from the interference of others. If someone wants to know about Jehovah’s people today, it is much better to ask them directly, rather than consult the disaffected or the cynical. If Nicodemus decided to follow Jesus, he had much to lose if Jesus turned out to be a fraud. Nicodemus took his

position as a ruler of the Jews seriously—his example would affect others. He had a great responsibility to make sure his decisions are made thoughtfully. By coming to Christ at night, Nicodemus “wished to conceal, not an evil deed from good men, but a good deed from evil men” (Plummer).

“I would only say that, if he felt it dangerous to be seen in the company of Jesus, it was a bold thing to visit Him at all ... And would that there were more like him, who, whether cautious to excess or not, do still feel constrained to judge for themselves about Christ” (Dods).

Jesus was not critical of Nicodemus’s decision to come to see him at night. Indeed, we would be so glad to meet a Nicodemus today, one who came to our home for a nocturnal confidential discussion. One only has to compare him to his fellow members of the Sanhedrin, who at this very moment are “already muttering their irritated resentment at this impudent intruder into their province ... and [his] ugly disregard for authority” (Gossip). Nicodemus is very different to his peers, who sneeringly said to him: “Not one of the rulers or of the Pharisees has put faith in [Jesus], has he?” (John 7:48).

The episode starts with the statement that Nicodemus has arrived in the night and ends with reference to the night—the darkness is all around them. Jesus’s conclusion is all about the conflict between light (himself) and darkness (the sinful world): “Now this is the basis for judgement: that the light has come into the world, but men have loved the darkness rather than the light, for their works were wicked. For whoever practises vile things hates the light and does not come to the light, so that his works may not be reproved. But whoever does what is true comes to the light, so that his works may be made manifest as having been done in harmony with God” (verses 19–21). Although Jesus does not refer directly to his interviewer, nor is he critical of Nicodemus’s choice of the night, this conclusion is a plea to Nicodemus to come out of the darkness and into the light.

Nicodemus’s first words about the signs Jesus is performing show that he is potentially in the same camp as those fickle people that Jesus did not trust. In fact, he uses the same words that John had used to describe those that Jesus would not trust. In addition, he does not say: ‘I know that you have come from God’, but “we know”. This is certainly an indication that he has been discussing the matter of

Jesus with his friends and with his colleagues of the Sanhedrin. It is reported that “the people of Jerusalem and all Judea and all the country around the Jordan were going out to” John the Baptist, even the Pharisees and the Sadducees (Matthew 3:5–7). “This is the witness John gave when the Jews sent priests and Levites from Jerusalem to ask him: ‘Who are you?’” (John 1:19).

More than that, during this Passover Festival, Jesus “drove all those with the sheep and cattle out of the temple, and he poured out the coins of the money changers and overturned their tables” (John 2:15). Nicodemus may well have witnessed this dramatic act of courage.

By saying “we know that you have come from God as a teacher, for no one can perform these signs that you perform unless God is with him”, is Nicodemus putting himself in the same category as the crowds at the Passover Festival, who “put their faith in his name when they saw the signs that he was performing”? However, Nicodemus’s emphasis is not on the signs. In fact, Nicodemus has responded to the signs in just the right way—they have led him to Jesus to learn from him as a *teacher*. Here is a man not out to trap Jesus, but to learn. He addresses him as Rabbi, the title of a teacher of spiritual things. Jesus must surely have been impressed with Nicodemus’s respect for him. Very few Pharisees and members of the Sanhedrin came this far with their faith. Nicodemus’s humble attitude turns out to be ideal for someone to enter the Kingdom and rule with Christ over the Earth (Revelation 5:10).

In response Jesus said to him: “Most truly I say to you, unless anyone is born again, he cannot see the Kingdom of God”. (verse 3)

Jesus uses his famous emphatic phrase ἀμὴν ἀμὴν to stress the utter reliability of what he is about to say. It is also an appropriate introduction to his remarkable assertion that it is not just Jews who will be entering the Kingdom, “anyone” who is “born again” will be able to do so.

At that time, the Kingdom of God was a hot topic amongst the Jews, especially as they rankled under the oppression of Rome and dreamt of the return of their Davidic kings. Many were “waiting for Jerusalem’s deliverance” (Luke 2:38). The preaching of John the Baptist heightened expectations when he announced: “Repent, for the Kingdom of the heavens has drawn near” (Matthew 3:3). Jesus repeated the same

imperative (Matthew 4:17). The Jews yearned for the arrival of the Kingdom of God. Knowing Nicodemus's expectations, Jesus decides to address this very topic. John has just told us that Jesus "knew what was in man" (2:25), so we can be sure that this subject is foremost in Nicodemus's mind and heart. However, as is evident from Nicodemus's response, Jesus knows that Nicodemus's expectations are at variance to the reality. How far will the teacher get in changing this pupil's assumptions?

Often Jesus uses a cryptic metaphor to get his audience engaged in the conversation, only for his audience to take the metaphor literally. This happened with his reference to living water when talking to the Samaritan woman (4:11, 12), with his saying that Lazarus was asleep (11:12) and with his reference to eating his flesh and drinking his blood when talking to new disciples of his (6:52, 60).

The RSV and the NIV comment in footnotes to "born again" that the phrase can equally be translated "born from above". Notice how the Greek word *ἀνωθεν*, which occurs thirteen times in the Bible, is variously translated:

"And the curtain of the sanctuary was torn in two *from top* (*ἀνωθεν*) to bottom", Mark 15:38,

"I resolved also, because I have traced all things *from the start* (*ἀνωθεν*) with accuracy", Luke 1:3,

"The one who comes *from above* (*ἀνωθεν*) is over all others", John 3:31,

"You would have no authority over me at all unless it had been granted to you *from above* (*ἀνωθεν*)", John 19:11,

"The inner garment was without a seam, being woven *from top* (*ἀνωθεν*) to bottom", John 19:23,

"The manner of life I led from youth up among my people ... is well-known by all the Jews who were *previously* (*ἀνωθεν*) acquainted with me", Acts 26:4, 5,

"How is it that you are turning back again to the weak and beggarly elementary things and want to slave for them over *again* (*ἀνωθεν*)?", Galatians 4:9,

"Every good gift and every perfect present is *from above* (*ἀνωθεν*)", James 1:17,

"This is not the wisdom that comes down *from above* (*ἀνωθεν*)...The wisdom *from above* (*ἀνωθεν*) is first of all pure", James 3:15, 17,

As you can see, ἄνωθεν is translated as ‘from above/top/beginning’ in every other case except Galatians 4:9.

So, what did Jesus mean when he used ἄνωθεν? Did he mean “born *again*” or “born *from above*”? Or did he mean both? Of course, we know what Nicodemus thought he meant, he thought he meant “again”. Robertson says: “The misapprehension of Nicodemus does not prove the meaning of Jesus. In the other passages in John (3:31; 19:11, 23) the meaning is ‘from above’ (*desuper* [Vg “from above”]) and usually so in the Synoptics. It is second birth, to be sure, regeneration, but a birth from above by the Spirit.” The Baptist scholar Merrill C. Tenney, made this comment “*Anothen*, which NIV and many others translate as “again,” in the Johannine writings normally means “from above,” and it should be rendered thus here.”

However, a conversation between a ruler of the Jews and Jesus, even though Nicodemus is a Greek name, is unlikely to have been carried out in Greek. There is not a Hebrew equivalent with such a dual meaning. Perhaps Jesus said in Hebrew that Nicodemus needed to be born again *and* born from above. All we can say is that when John’s Gospel was written in Greek, God oversaw the word choice, and ἄνωθεν is an ideal way of using a polysemic word with two appropriate meanings.

The metaphor of rebirth is significant. Ever since Adam rejected Jehovah as his father mankind has been cast out of God’s family. Having been born into Adam’s family we are born into a life of sin, but God wants us back in his family. If we choose to return, then a regeneration can occur: “God made you alive, though you were dead in your trespasses and sins” (Ephesians 2:1). Those who welcome Jesus are reborn. “To all who did receive him, he gave authority to become God’s children, because they were exercising faith in his name. And they were born, not from blood or from a fleshly will or from man’s will, but from God” (John 1:12, 13). Although we might wish to be reborn, it is not in our powers to do it, this is only achieved by God’s will. This is true of the metaphor. Birth is something initiated not by the baby, but by the father: “Praised be the God and Father of our Lord Jesus Christ, for according to his great mercy *he* gave us a new birth” (1 Peter 1:3).

Nicodemus said to him: “How can a man be born when he is old? He cannot enter into the womb of his mother a second time and be born, can he?” (verse 4)

After Nicodemus’s impressive introduction in verse 1, this response is quite a disappointment. One would have expected him to take Jesus’s words as a trope, instead Nicodemus embarrassingly takes them literally. It is not as if the idea of spiritual rebirth or its need is difficult to understand. In fact, later, Jesus joins with us in our surprise at Nicodemus’s response.

It is not Jesus’s words about the Kingdom of God that are a surprise for him, but it is the manner of entry that puzzles Nicodemus. Jesus sets a big test for this foremost Pharisee, this ruler of the Jews, at the pinnacle of his profession and faith. Jesus asks him to become like a baby.

Jesus answered: “Most truly I say to you, unless anyone is born from water and spirit, he cannot enter into the Kingdom of God” (verse 5)

Once again Jesus introduces his comment with ἀμὴν ἀμὴν. It looks as if Jesus wants us to compare this comment with his earlier statement.

Most truly I say to you, unless anyone is born again, he cannot see the Kingdom of God

Most truly I say to you, unless anyone is born from water and spirit, he cannot enter into the Kingdom

Through this parallelism, “born again” is explained as being “born from water and spirit”. Jesus’s baptism helps us to understand this rebirth from water and spirit. He dedicated his life to his Father’s service (Psalm 40:7, 8). After his baptism, his Father proclaimed: “This is my Son, the beloved, whom I have approved” (Matthew 3:17). This is the moment when Jesus was born again; the moment he became the Christ—the anointed; the moment that he was baptised into death (Romans 6:3–5).

Jesus likens our conversion to Christianity to returning to become children again: “Truly I say to you, unless you turn around and become as young children, you will by no means enter into the Kingdom of the heavens” (Matthew 18:1).

This idea of a new birth through baptism is present also in Paul’s words at Titus 3:5: “[God] saved us by means of the bath that brought us to life and by making us new by holy spirit”.

Peter says: “Praised be the God and Father of our Lord Jesus Christ, for according to

his great mercy he gave us a new birth ... For you have been given a new birth, not by corruptible, but by incorruptible seed, through the word of the living and enduring God ... As newborn infants, form a longing for the unadulterated milk of the word, so that by means of it you may grow to salvation” (1 Peter 1:3, 23; 2:2).

John too refers to this rebirth in his letters: “If you know that he is righteous, you also know that everyone who practises righteousness has been born from him” (1 John 2:29). “Everyone who has been born from God does not practise sin, for His seed remains in such one, and he cannot practise sin, for he has been born from God” (1 John 3:9). “Beloved ones, let us continue loving one another, because love is from God, and everyone who loves has been born from God and knows God” (1 John 4:7). “Everyone who believes that Jesus is the Christ has been born from God, and everyone who loves the one who caused to be born loves him who has been born from that one ... We know that everyone who has been born from God does not practise sin, but the one born from God watches him” (1 John 5:1, 18).

Water baptism is the public display of a person’s private dedication to God. It could be seen as a complete immersion into the will of God—disowning self (Matthew 16:24). Of course, anyone can be baptised, but whether that baptism is also a rebirth is determined by God. In the case of Cornelius this spiritual adoption occurred *before* water baptism, causing Peter to exclaim: “Can anyone deny water to prevent these from being baptized who have received the holy spirit just as we have?” (Acts 10:47). This was the moment when they “received a spirit of adoption as sons, by which spirit [they] cry out: ‘Abba, Father!’” (Romans 8:15).

In verse 3, Jesus had said that those who are born again would “see the Kingdom of God”. Here in verse 5, Jesus expands on the word “see” by defining it as *entering* the Kingdom. What is the Kingdom of God? When Jesus was asked to teach his disciples how to pray, he gave them a model prayer, now called the Lord’s Prayer. He instructed us to pray: “Let your Kingdom come. Let your will take place, as in heaven, also on earth” (Matthew 6:10). So, this Kingdom will “come” from Heaven to perform God’s will on Earth. Daniel 2:44 informs us that the Kingdom of God will bring devastation to all the kingdoms of the Earth, replacing them as Earth’s only rulership: “In the days of those kings the God of heaven will set up a kingdom that will never be destroyed. And this kingdom will not be passed on to any other people. It will crush

and put an end to all these kingdoms, and it alone will stand forever” (cf Psalm 2). Jesus promised his apostles that they would rule together with him in his Kingdom: “You are the ones who have stuck with me in my trials; and I make a covenant with you, just as my Father has made a covenant with me, for a kingdom, so that you may eat and drink at my table in my Kingdom, and sit on thrones to judge the twelve tribes of Israel” (Luke 22:28–30).

As Paul faced execution, he encouraged Timothy by saying: “If we go on enduring, we will also rule together as kings” (2 Timothy 2:12).

John was given this vision of the Kingdom: “And I saw thrones, and those who sat on them were given authority to judge. Yes, I saw the souls of those executed for the witness they gave about Jesus and for speaking about God, and those who had not worshipped the wild beast or its image and had not received the mark on their forehead and on their hand. And they came to life and ruled as kings with the Christ for a thousand years” (Revelation 20:4).

What has been born from the flesh is flesh, and what has been born from the spirit is spirit. (verse 6)

Is this a technical point, a literal comment along the lines of: “I tell you this, brothers, that flesh and blood cannot inherit God’s Kingdom” (1 Corinthians 15:50)? In order to enter the Kingdom of the Heavens a person will need a new body: “It is sown a physical body; it is raised up a spiritual body” (1 Corinthians 15:44).

Or is this instance of flesh and spirit in line with: “Keep walking by spirit and you will carry out no fleshly desire at all” (Galatians 5:16)? In other words, is ‘flesh’ a reference to a sinful life, and ‘spirit’ a reference to living in accordance with God’s will? This new birth happens before entry into Heaven, so it is more likely that Jesus is using flesh and spirit in the second sense. Of course, this stage prepares for entry into Heaven as a spirit.

Do not be amazed because I told you: You people must be born again. (verse 7)

Nicodemus’s face must have been full of wonder and bewilderment. A Gentile who converted to Judaism was said to be born again. So, to be born again as a proselyte was not a new idea, in fact the Talmud makes mention of such a metaphorical process,

but for “you people”—the Jews, the descendents of Abraham—this was bewildering for Nicodemus. John the Baptist had said: “Do not start saying to yourselves: ‘We have Abraham as our father’. For I say to you that God is able to raise up children for Abraham from these stones” (Luke 7:8).

The wind blows where it wants to, and you hear the sound of it, but you do not know where it comes from and where it is going. So it is with everyone who has been born from the spirit. (verse 8)

As Nicodemus and Jesus chatted into the night, a breeze may have rustled the leaves. Wind and spirit is the same word in Greek. You cannot see either the wind or the spirit. All we can detect is the effect of the wind: how the leaves move and how the tree bends. Likewise, we can tell if someone is “born from the spirit” because they respond to the influence of the spirit in their lives, they are submissive to the one who sends the spirit and to his authority.

The wind is also beyond the control of man. We cannot command the wind to do our bidding. So likewise, it is not in our power to be born from the spirit; this is a decision that is made “from above”.

Why would Jesus have made this point to Nicodemus? Because the Jews had become smug about their descent from Abraham, and this had caused them to become complacent about their relationship with God. Nothing can be more dangerous. “Keep testing whether you are in the faith; keep proving what you yourselves are” (2 Corinthians 13:5). The proof of who we are—our faith—does not reside in the faith of our parents, as Paul put it: “He is a Jew who is one on the inside, and his circumcision is that of the heart by spirit” (Romans 2:28).

In addition to this, the time was coming rapidly for the New Covenant, when God would sign a new agreement where the former national distinctions would be no longer relevant (Galatians 3:28).

In answer Nicodemus said to him: “How can these things be?” (verse 9)

Nicodemus is all at sea. As a Jew he is in a special covenant with God already; as a Pharisee, he believes that salvation is by sedulously following the Mosaic Law and the interpretation of it by the Rabbis.

Jesus replied: "Are you a teacher of Israel and yet do not know these things?" (verse 10)

Jesus uses a definite article in front of "teacher". The NIV seems to pick up on this by translating Jesus's words: "You are Israel's teacher... and do you not understand these things?" ASV shows the definite article: "Art thou *the* teacher of Israel, and understandest not these things?" Does this imply that Nicodemus is the pre-eminent teacher in Israel at the time?

Jesus is surprised that such a distinguished teacher in Israel would not know the meaning of his words.

Jehovah had used the same idea of regeneration by water and spirit when he spoke to the exiled nation in Babylon: "I will take you out of the nations and collect you together out of all the lands and bring you in upon your soil. And I will sprinkle upon you clean water, and you will become clean; from all your impurities and from all your dungy idols I shall cleanse you. And I will give you a new heart, and a new spirit I shall put inside you, and I will take away the heart of stone from your flesh and give you a heart of flesh. And my spirit I shall put inside you, and I will act so that in my regulations you will walk, and my judicial decisions you will keep and actually carry out. And you will certainly dwell in the land that I gave to your forefathers, and you must become my people and I myself shall become your God" (Ezekiel 36:24–28).

Even with this reference in Ezekiel, even we do not find Jesus's wording entirely easy to comprehend. But Jesus's disbelief in Nicodemus's ignorance must of course have been genuine. A man like Nicodemus should have known how to gain entry into the Kingdom of God.

The idea of being washed of our impurities is an attractive one. We rejoice in the cleansing by the blood of Jesus; we enjoy a clean standing in God's eyes as a result. But we yearn for the day when we will be truly clean—perfect in God's eyes.

Most truly I say to you, what we know we speak, and what we have seen we bear witness to, but you do not receive the witness we give. (verse 11)

Who is Jesus referring to when he uses the first person plural pronoun? Who join

Christ in speaking and bearing witness? “Nicodemus represents the half-believing Jews who were impressed by Jesus’ signs but had not reached an adequate faith in him... Jesus, on the other hand, it seems, associates with himself his disciples who have seen, believed, and known” (Barrett). “The Lord and those with Him, of whom some, including the Evangelist, may have been present at the interview, appear to stand in contrast to the group represented by Nicodemus... They were already gathered round Christ those who had had personal (*we have seen*) and immediate (*we know*) knowledge of the divine wonders which He announced” (Westcott).

If I have told you earthly things and you still do not believe, how will you believe if I tell you heavenly things? (verse 12)

Presumably, the “earthly things” are the physical metaphors that Jesus is using to help Nicodemus understand spiritual or “heavenly things”. Jesus had referred to birth and to the wind, both things that Nicodemus would have believed in. However, it is not the “earthly” that is at issue here, but the “heavenly”. If Nicodemus cannot comprehend the connections between the metaphor and the reality, how will he comprehend if Jesus just tells him heavenly things without these earthly analogies?

Moreover, no man has ascended into heaven but the one who descended from heaven, the Son of man. (verse 13)

As Jesus said, no human had yet gone to Heaven. Peter concurred when he stated: “David did not ascend to the heavens” (Acts 2:34). John the Baptist also died before Jesus, and so, even though he was the greatest man who had ever lived “a lesser person in the Kingdom of the heavens is greater than he is” (Matthew 11:11). All those who died before Jesus did not go to Heaven. This is because they died before Jesus, the “forerunner”, went to Heaven (Hebrews 6:20). In so doing, Jesus “opened up... a new and living way” into Heaven (Hebrews 10:20).

But, why did Jesus say to Nicodemus that no one had yet gone to Heaven from the Earth at this moment in the conversation?

Nicodemus did not comprehend this divine teaching about being in the Kingdom of God. Was there any way that he could learn about this? No one on Earth could

instruct him about it because no one had been in Heaven and thus in a position to explain anything about getting into the Kingdom. The only exception was Jesus. Jesus could teach Nicodemus and others because Jesus had descended from Heaven and was qualified to instruct people about such things (w 2006:6:15:30).

If this was the case, why was Jesus so surprised at Nicodemus's difficulties in comprehension? Evidently, Jesus's surprise was more to do with Nicodemus's incomprehension with his 'earthly' metaphors. If Nicodemus was struggling at this stage how would he graduate to understanding 'heavenly things' brought by "the one who descended from heaven" (verse 13)?

Jesus uses the term "son of man" to refer to himself. He did not, as angels had done so before, come as a materialised spirit, but he was actually born as a man. In a very real sense he had been born again. This meant that he was now the equivalent of Adam when Adam was perfect, and he had become the second Adam (1 Corinthians 15:45, 47). Jesus was now capable of paying the corresponding ransom price (ἀντίλυτρον, 1 Timothy 2:6).

"The designation 'Son of man,' therefore, also serves to identify Jesus Christ as the great Kinsman of mankind, having the power to redeem them from bondage to sin and death, as well as to identify him as the great Avenger of blood.—Le 25:48, 49; Nu 35:1-29" (*Insight*).

And just as Moses lifted up the serpent in the wilderness, so the Son of man must be lifted up, so that everyone believing in him may have everlasting life. (verse 14, 15)

Once again Jesus starts with a metaphor. No Jew would have suspected that the event that Jesus refers to was a Messianic prophecy. But Nicodemus would know about the event, and Jesus will endeavour to take Nicodemus further spiritually, just as Nicodemus had hoped.

Jesus has just said that "no man has ascended into heaven but the one who descended from heaven, the Son of man". Now he talks about the ascension he will have to make before his return to Heaven. He does so using a metaphor loaded with meaning.

Towards the end of their forty years in the wilderness, Israel "kept speaking against God and Moses" (Numbers 21:5). This rebellion was led by the remaining generation

of those who had lived in Egypt. Jehovah punished them by sending venomous snakes, killing many. As a result the people showed contrition and begged for the removal of the snakes. Jehovah agreed, but this left many who had been bitten facing death. Jehovah told Moses: “Make for yourself a fiery snake and place it upon a signal pole. And it must occur that when anyone has been bitten, he then has to look at it and so must keep alive” (verse 8).

Rather than just healing those who had been bitten, Jehovah first required an act of faith to prove their contrition. They had to go and look at the bronze serpent on the top of the pole. “The vivid story is an uncomplicated parable of God’s astonishing grace. He presents his gift of salvation to undeserving rebels who have despised his gifts, spurned his mercy, rejected his word and slandered his name” (Brown).

The parable has other points of importance. The serpent was lifted high on a pole so that the remedy was widely available. “Issues of race, gender, achievements, status and experience may well have significance in other contexts, but not in the quest for eternal salvation... The youngest member of the community could do it as easily as the oldest traveller. Weak or strong, ignorant or erudite, poor or prosperous, all were alike dependent on that single look” (*ibid*).

What a cluster of ideas are attached to Jesus’s citation: we have God’s grace towards sinners who repent, the idea of an antidote to the results of sin, the opportunity for all to avail themselves of this cure, the need for faith to gain salvation and the ransom sacrifice. Jesus’s next words to Nicodemus would emphasise this global application.

For God loved the world so much that he gave his only-begotten Son, so that everyone exercising faith in him might not be destroyed but have everlasting life. (verse 16)

The connections between the copper serpent in the wilderness and Jesus’s famous statement are now obvious.

Mankind has rebelled against God; God has cursed them, they are full of the poison of sin and death; they will shortly all die. In spite of this, God still loves them and ardently wants everyone to “exercise faith” in his means of salvation. A great opportunity has been given, one available to all, whatever race, age, gender, education. If they want to be saved from certain death, they have to get up from

their bed, go out of their tent and gaze in faith at God's Son impaled and lifted up for all to see.

It is so clear now why “might not be destroyed” precedes “but have everlasting life”. Just as all those bitten Israelites were going to die—be destroyed—unless they obeyed Jehovah and acted urgently, so all are going to be destroyed today unless they look in faith to the Son. The love of God is accepted by this simple act.

The look of faith is far more than belief. The Greek word πιστεύων is an active present participle, and it is followed by εἰς. “[A] construction which is common in the New Testament (especially in John's Gospel) is πιστεύω with εἰς and the accusative case ... The whole construction of εἰς plus the accusative must be translated rather than attempting to translate the preposition εἰς as an isolated word. Faith is thought of as an activity, as something men do, i.e. putting faith into someone” (Kaufman).

The value of something is always what someone is prepared to pay for it. Our value to God is equivalent to the value of his “only-begotten Son”. God has gone that far in demonstrating his love for us individually. No sacrifice on God's part was made in the wilderness to rescue those contrite complainers, apart from re-exposing himself to being hurt once more. But to rescue those who can be rescued today, a great act of self-sacrifice was undertaken. It amounted to the two greatest acts of love ever made.

“Jehovah does much to prove his love for us. Surely, Christ's ransom sacrifice is the most potent answer to the satanic lie that we are worthless or unlovable. Never should we forget that the agonizing death Jesus suffered on the torture stake and the even greater agony Jehovah endured in watching his beloved Son's death were proof of their love for us. Moreover, that love applies to us personally. That is how the apostle Paul saw it, for he wrote: ‘The Son of God ... loved me and handed himself over for me.’—Galatians 2:20” (*w* 1995:4:1:14:17).

The remorseful Israelites in the wilderness took the initiative and came to Jehovah to plead for forgiveness and salvation. But now it is reversed. Jehovah's “love is in this respect, not that we have loved God, but that he loved us and sent his Son as a propitiatory sacrifice for our sins” (1 John 4:10). The consequence of Jehovah taking the initiative makes a profound difference.

First, we do not need to regain the favour of Jehovah, to propitiate him. Sometimes people picture Jesus pleading our cause in front of the Heavenly throne. This is not

the case. God loves us first. The propitiation is given by God to satisfy the demands of justice.

Second, God loves all—the lovable and the unlovable, the spiritual, the aspiritual and the unspiritual, the good and the bad. In the wilderness all those affected knew the dangerous state that they were in. Today, people generally do not. A global witness is required—the testimony to all the inhabited Earth (Matthew 24:14). Jehovah took the initiative in his love and sacrificed his Son, now he has taken the initiative to inform everyone of the means of salvation.

Third, it means the relationship that we have with our God is altogether better. If we had gone to God and asked him for his friendship—pleaded for his love—that would have created a very different relationship—one in which we would have had to continue to convince Jehovah of our worthiness. But, the perfect God came to imperfect you and me and said, I want to be your friend. That entirely redefines the relationship. We do not have to grovel or plead or convince him to love us; it was *his* idea. That is astonishingly liberating.

God did not just send but he “gave his only-begotten Son”. Since Adam’s rebellion, mankind has been incapable of returning to God’s family. God’s Son is a gift; we did not earn him. As a result, we have the opportunity to avail ourselves of the gift of a relationship with our Heavenly Father, and so to gain everlasting life.

All of this intense divine love for the world “would be a revelation to the exclusive Pharisee, brought up to believe that God loved only the chosen people” (Plummer). When Jesus refers to himself as God’s “only-begotten Son” he must be making a direct allusion to Jehovah’s words to Abraham: “Take, please, your son, your only son whom you so love, Isaac, and travel to the land of Moriah and offer him up there as a burnt offering on one of the mountains that I will designate to you” (Genesis 22:2). Did Nicodemus see the reference? In order that none of us are unaware of what God must have gone through, we are given a human example.

The uniqueness, the truly special nature of the Son, the remarkable status of the gift is emphasised in Jesus saying “*only-begotten*”. That uniqueness lies in Jesus being the first one God created, and the only one that God has created on his own (Colossians 1:15; Revelation 3:14).

Now that God had given his all, Paul could declare: “Since he did not even spare his own Son but handed him over for us all, will he not also, along with him, kindly give us all other things?” (Romans 8:32).

Here the little word “so” does not occur in the Hebrew of Genesis 22:2, but it does appear in the Greek of John 3:16. What a small word “so” is, but what an impact it has on Jesus’s statement. This tiny word wipes out our quibbles over our inadequacies, and our doubts that the perfect God can love someone who repeatedly sins. In that tiny word so, lies all the yearning of Jehovah to have us back, all his begging, all his anguish, all his readiness to forgive.

For God did not send his Son into the world for him to judge the world, but for the world to be saved through him. (verse 17)

Once more the verse begins with “for”. We are invited to make a connection. Let us compare verses 16 and 17. Here they are reordered as Hebrew parallel thoughts:

16a For God loved the world so much that he gave his only-begotten Son

17a For God did not send his Son into the world for him to judge the world

16b so that everyone exercising faith in him might not be destroyed but have everlasting life

17b but for the world to be saved through him

As if God’s motive is not clear enough in verse 16a, Jesus gives more detail in 17a. Since God “does not desire anyone to be destroyed but desires all to attain to repentance” (2 Peter 3:9), Jesus’s mission was a mission of salvation. So the “destruction” in verse 16b is not God’s priority. “He is not seeking an excuse to condemn men” (Tenney), but all his efforts are directed at saving them. Jesus later said: “If anyone hears my sayings and does not keep them, I do not judge him; for I came, not to judge the world, but to save the world” (John 12:47). We have all been judged adversely as sons of Adam, and we will all one day be judged, but at present there is mercy, a period of favour to be seized. Thankfully, some, during this period of God’s favour, recognise Jesus’s motive and respond like the inhabitants of Sychar: “We know that this man really is the saviour of the world” (John 4:42).

Salvation initiated by God is not connected with innocence, but with the response to God’s initiative.

God's loving motive is also highlighted by 16a "gave" preceding 17a "send".

The word translated "send" is not πέμπω, but ἀποστέλλω. "In the NT as a whole πέμπω seems to be used when the stress is on the sending, ἀποστέλλω when it is on the commission... In John, Jesus uses ἀποστέλλω to denote his full authority" (TDNT).

In 16a Jesus says God loved the world and gave his Son; in 17a Jesus says that God sent his Son *into* the world. The world can be loved from a distance, but God sent his Son *into* it, to show His love in it rather than from a distance.

Notice the threefold use of the word κόσμος; "For God did not send his Son into the *world* for him to judge the *world*, but for the *world* to be saved through him." What a shift of emphasis this was for Nicodemus and the Jews. Here was the opportunity for salvation for anyone, something that it took even the apostles a while to comprehend. If Peter was present during Jesus's conversation with Nicodemus, then the moment when Peter finally understood Jesus's words occurred six years later in the home of Cornelius. Peter said: "Now I truly understand that God is not partial, but in every nation the man who fears him and does what is right is acceptable to him" (Acts 10:34, 35).

The world is to be saved *through* Jesus. Since "All things came into existence *through* him" (John 1:3), then how fitting that Jesus should be the one sent to save the world. His love for what he had had such a part in making moved him to act (Proverbs 8:31). He was to be the "mediator between God and men" (1 Timothy 2:5).

Whoever exercises faith in him is not to be judged. Whoever does not exercise faith has been judged already, because he has not exercised faith in the name of the only-begotten Son of God. (verse 18)

"Judgment was not the object of Christ's mission, judgment is in fact the necessary result of it. This judgment is self-executed" (Westcott).

Throughout these verses Jesus's careful use of tenses is illuminating. The change in tense midway through the second sentence is striking. The non-Christian has already been judged adversely, not by God, but by himself—it is self-inflicted. In the end, when the "sheep and the goats" are separated by Christ, the separation will have been made by the individuals themselves. By showing no faith in the Son of God

they will have already moved to Jesus's left-hand. However, Jesus wants to stress that at this moment this state is not irredeemable. Jesus is appealing to Nicodemus to exercise faith in the Son of God and move from judgement to salvation. This is the time to go from 'having been judged' to 'having everlasting life' (John 3:36). If asked what are the most significant moments in their life, people would perhaps say their graduation, their first job, their marriage, the birth of their first child and so on. It will be a shock to find out the most important moment of their lives was none of these. No, it was that Saturday morning when the door bell rang and two of Jesus's witnesses endeavoured to talk to them about the good news of the Kingdom, and they said they were too busy. That tiny moment, lasting no longer than a quarter of a minute, was the most significant moment in their entire existence. The contrast between their viewpoint and the viewpoint of the two witnesses at the door could not have been further apart. People are judged by their reaction. They remain in God's wrath (John 3:36) or escape. As Jesus spoke, people listened and reacted. Once the "good news of the Kingdom" has been "preached in all the inhabited earth *for a witness* to all the nations... then the end" can "come" (Matthew 24:14). Everyone will have had sufficient testimony to make their choice, or at least they will have made a choice as to listen to that testimony or not.

Nicodemus must have had so many significant moments in his life—his magnificent graduation from the Rabbinical school, his appointment to the Sanhedrin, his judgements, his publications, his honours, his marriage, his beautiful children, his grand parties—yet none of this is mentioned. The most significant moment in Nicodemus's life from God's point of view was his nocturnal discussion with Jesus.

Now this is the basis for judgement: that the light has come into the world, but men have loved the darkness rather than the light, for their works were wicked. (verse 19)

In Jesus's concluding comments, he once more draws a metaphor from the moment. Nicodemus "came to [Jesus] in the night" (verse 2); from the darkness he had been drawn to the light. He was drawn to the "teacher" who could illuminate the darkness of ignorance. He had found that his ignorance was rather more than he thought. In his concluding appeal Jesus entreats Nicodemus to continue this journey further towards the light.

We need to pay attention once more to the tenses here. In these tenses there is all the hope of God. “Men *have* loved the darkness” and “their works *were* wicked”, but the present and the future can now be so different. By sending the means of salvation—his Son—God is making a strong appeal to all to come to the light.

Westcott highlights the word order at the end of this verse: “The order of the original is very remarkable. Its force might be suggested in English by the inversion, ‘for evil were their works’”.

Once the copper serpent was erected on its pole, those Israelites who writhed about in pain in the darkness of their sin and the darkness of their tents now had a choice. They could remain in their darkness or come out into the light and gaze up at God’s means of salvation. It seems extraordinary that some might have doggedly remained on their beds and died in agony. Equally, when the end comes for this world, many will be doggedly prevaricating and procrastinating over the all important decision to come to the light.

For whoever practises vile things hates the light and does not come to the light, so that his works may not be reproved. (verse 20)

“The temporary enjoyment of sin” (Hebrews 11:25) is too potent for many. Because it is temporary, they want to repeat it over and over again, and so it becomes a practice. Their love of vile things prevents them from ever finding the light attractive. They not only do not want to be seen and reproved by others, but they do not want to be seen and reproved by themselves; they do not want to see what they are—they avert their gaze from the mirror (James 1:22–25), so as not to see “the true value of the inanities which fill up [their] existence” (Plummer).

The Greek word translated “reproved” can also mean “exposed”, as light exposes what is taking place in the darkness. “Keep on making sure of what is acceptable to the Lord; and stop sharing in the unfruitful works that belong to the darkness; rather, expose them for what they are. For the things they do in secret are shameful even to mention. Now all the things that are being exposed are made evident by the light, for everything that is being made evident is light. Therefore, it is said: “Awake, O sleeper, and arise from the dead, and the Christ will shine upon you” (Ephesians 5:10–14).

But whoever does what is true comes to the light, so that his works may be made manifest as having been done in harmony with God. (verse 21)

The last two sentences of Jesus are in parallel:

For whoever practises vile things hates the light and does not come to the light,

so that his works may not be reproved.

But whoever does what is true comes to the light,

so that his works may be made manifest as having been done in harmony with God.

Jesus contrasts ‘practising vile things’ with ‘doing what is true’. Nicodemus had momentarily ceased to ‘practise vile things’ and now had done “what is true” by coming to the light.

It is one thing to know what is true, it is entirely another to do what is true. “Truth is the cry of all, but the game of the few” (Berkeley). There is something so attractive about the truth, but so very demanding in practice. If “we go on walking in the darkness, we are lying and are not practising the truth” (1 John 1:6). But it is only when we do what is true that we come into the light of God’s approval, and it is really only when we practise the truth that we come to understand its wisdom and glory.

Many of Nicodemus’s peers stayed away from Jesus, they had no desire to be reproved. Courage is needed in order to come to the light and have one’s life exposed to it. Nicodemus comes to Jesus and in the light of what Jesus says is reproved. But in the end, just after Jesus dies, Nicodemus will make his faith manifest and will act in harmony with his God.

We certainly do not have to be perfect to want to come to the light and have its brilliance expose our lives and our thoughts and motives. David asked: “Examine me, O Jehovah, and put me to the test; refine my innermost thoughts and my heart” (Psalm 26:2). David wanted to be examined so that he could be refined. Nicodemus too wanted that same process to happen to him (1 John 1:8, 9).

Paradoxically, we come to the light and realise our flaws, our unrighteousness, but when we come to the light Jehovah has an opposite view of us—he views us as righteous for coming to the light.

Presumably there were some final salutations between the two men, yet the text is so silent. It is as if Nicodemus was given so much to think about that his comments become shorter and shorter until he says nothing more and he just silently slips away into the darkness with a mind and heart full of the words of Jesus.

Both Nicodemus and Jesus make three speeches. Nicodemus's get shorter while Jesus's get longer. The word count is revealing. Nicodemus's three speeches amount to 24/18/4; while the word count for Jesus's is 16/70/220. Nicodemus speaks 46 words; Jesus 306.

There are 352 words in all, the centre point is at the end of verse 12.

As Nicodemus fades out of the encounter, Jesus becomes less personal. Notice how the pronouns gradually go from second person singular to second person plural and then disappear altogether: v.2: first person plural; v.3: second person singular; v.4: third person singular; v.5–7a: second person singular; v.7b: second person plural; v.8: second person singular; v.9: no pronouns; v.10: second person singular; v.11, 12: first person plural; v.13–21: no pronouns.

This fading out of Nicodemus is intriguing. Of course, I assume we only have a very small part of their conversation—the highlights. Nonetheless, the holy spirit chose to end with a monologue by Jesus rather than any response from Nicodemus. Ultimately, we are the audience and the ellipsis is for us to fill. Jesus's final words are a plea to Nicodemus and these words form his conclusion to the meeting.

In this introductory episode about Nicodemus he has three speeches, and there are three episodes about Nicodemus—one at the beginning, one in the middle and one at the end of Jesus's ministry. In the second episode he makes just one comment, but it is in Jesus's defence, and in the face of hostile peer pressure. In the final episode where he aligns himself with Jesus, disowning his past, he is silent as he brings his tribute. The three episodes show us a growing faith: investigation, defence, dedication. So, in a sense, Nicodemus's reaction to Jesus's words in his first encounter is left until we hear his defence of Jesus in front of his fellow rulers (John 7:45–52), and then ultimately as the sun was setting on the 14th Nisan 33 C.E. he fully emerged from the darkness and into the bright light, and all could see his new allegiance.

JESUS AND NICODEMUS

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APPENDIX

In the Bible the divine name יהוה occurs almost seven thousand times, more often than any of God's titles, and more often than any other separate Hebrew word.

There are many theophoric names in the Bible. The majority of Bible translators transliterate the first two syllables of those names as Jeho. Hence: Jehonathan, Jehoshua, Jehoshaphat, Jehoahaz, Jehonadab, Jehoram etc. When the Israelites shortened a name they would not abbreviate but they contracted it by removing syllables from the middle of the name. So Jehonathan was reduced to Jonathan; Jehoshua became Joshua; Jehonadab became Jonadab. God's name was contracted to Jah, hence: Elijah, Abijah and Hallelujah etc. Therefore, the divine name must have had three syllables, not two.

We believe that a י is more likely to be transliterated as a *y* in English, and a ו is more likely to be transliterated as a *w*. So the divine name could be *Yehowah*. However, most Bible scholars avoid any transliteration. They use the tetragrammaton in Hebrew letters יהוה, or they display the divine name as YHWH. This is all well and good, but it is inconsistent with their transliteration of other Bible names. If they are to be consistent then they should either use Yehonathan for Jonathan or show the Hebrew letters יהנתן, or YWNTN. Sometimes they use *Yahweh* which disregards how names were shortened, and it only has two syllables.

The argument that the vowels of יהוה are those of אֶדְנִי does not hold up because the vowels are not the same.

Gesenius pointed out that "Those who consider that יהוה was the actual pronunciation [of God's name] are not altogether without ground on which to defend their opinion. In this way can the abbreviated syllables יהו and יו, with which many proper names begin, be more satisfactorily explained."

We believe that *Jehovah* is a reasonable transliteration of the tetragrammaton.